

P2I Guide for conducting on site group discussions

November 2020

Lena Eichelbaum, Dennis Niesel, Nick Vilter, Nicolaus Wilder

Kiel University

Path2Integrity

**Rotatory role-playing and role-models
to enhance the research integrity culture**

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824488.

Table of contents

1	Introduction.....	3
2	Target Groups and Recruitment.....	3
3	Preparation of the Group Discussion	3
4	Conducting a Group Discussion.....	3
5	Data processing	4
5.1	Raw Audio Data.....	4
5.2	Transcription	4
5.3	Data Security	4
6	Appendix	5
6.1	Recruitment	5
6.2	Abstinence Principle	5
6.3	Question Types.....	5
6.3.1	Immanent Questioning.....	5
6.3.2	Exmanent Questioning	6
6.3.3	Direct Questions (Phase).....	6
6.4	Transcription	6
6.4.1	Clues.....	6
6.4.2	Transcription Rules.....	8
6.5	Protocol Template.....	9
6.6	Informed Consent Form.....	11

1 Introduction

Welcome to the guide to group discussions in the Path2Integrity evaluation. This document will guide you through the procedures of a how to lead a successful group discussion. The group discussions are part of the evaluation process of Path2Integrity and are intended to provide information about the sustainability and long-term efficiency of the learning units and campaign impact.

Thank you very much in advance for conducting the discussions.

2 Target Groups and Recruitment

The first step is to form a diverse group of participant, which in the best case scenario, can be recruited from the P2ILC programme.

- Optimal size of the group: 5-7 people
- Target group: students and academics with at least a Bachelor's degree who carry out research in the broadest sense and who can talk about their research in English or German
- Give interested parties a brief overview of the group discussion (see appendix 6.1)

3 Preparation of the Group Discussion

- **Room:**
 - find a secluded area far from disturbances for the group discussion
 - make sure that the group formation makes it viable for a round table discussion with enough space for everyone
 - please provide drinks
- **Technical Equipment:**
 - for the audio recording you'll need one or, if possible, two recording devices
 - test the devices and familiarise yourself with the technique in advance
 - if you are using two microphones: place them in the middle of the table, pointing in different directions
- **Informed Consent:**
 - Participants must sign the online informed consent form. The pdf-file (appendix VII) is just for their own records. It doesn't need to be signed and sent back.
 - To identify your group, a 2-digit group ID is necessary. It is generated from the first letter of your name and the number of the group discussions you have conducted. Example: Nick held his third group discussion → ID: N3
 - Send the informed consent pdf-form, the link to the [questionnaire](#) and the group ID in digital form to each participant a few days before the discussion
<https://path2integrity.eu/limesurvey/index.php/237937?lang=en>

4 Conducting a Group Discussion

The group discussion ideally takes 1–2hrs in total and can be divided into four different phases:

1. Warm-up

- Welcome all the participants and create a relaxed atmosphere
- Leave all audio recording devices switched off

2. Opening Phase

- Introduce yourself and the P2I project shortly
 - Explain the expectations of the group discussion:
 - The group should speak in its milieu-specific language
 - The group should talk to each other not to the moderator
 - The focus of the discussion should be on the participants' concrete experiences
 - Start the recording
 - Ask the following initial question and repeat it if necessary
- **Please tell us about your experience of responsible conduct of research in your everyday life as a student/researcher.**

3. Field Phase

- The group should at best be left to its own discussions (see Abstinence Principle, appendix 6.2)
- If the discussion comes to a standstill: don't make any **interventions for 5 minutes**
- If the participants do not generate a new self-running discussion: you can proceed with different question types (see appendix 6.3)

4. Final Phase

- Close the discussion and ask if there is anything left open to discuss (see appendix 6.3.3)
- Finish the audio recording and say goodbye to the participants
- Then fill out the seat-protocol (see appendix 6.5)

5 Data processing

5.1 Raw Audio Data

- The group discussion should only be partially transcribed, the identification of the relevant parts is carried out by CAU
- To do this please upload the audio-file via the P2I homepage, we will send you the relevant times of the passages that need to be transcribed

5.2 Transcription

- For the transcription, follow the transcription rules (see appendix 6.4.2)
- Name the transcript-file with the following code: Your name initials, day, month, year of the group discussion, each with two digits; example: AB260520
- When you are finished please upload the transcript-file via the P2I homepage
- Ensure that all names and personal data are made anonymous during the transcription process

5.3 Data Security

- Security of the data has the highest priority
- Please use the Path2Integrity homepage to ensure secure data transmission when sending data → upload the transcript and the audio file via the P2I homepage to the folder "WP documents / WP6"
- After uploading the data via the P2I homepage successfully, delete all non-anonymised data

If there are any issues, please contact us: evaluation@path2integrity.uni-kiel.de

6 Appendix

6.1 Recruitment

You should specify different basic data for the recruitment. You can use the following text:

Nowadays, with a growing research landscape, research integrity gets more and more important. It leads to reliable research results which are the basis for developing innovative solutions for the challenges of our time and thus for the future of our society. To make this relevance learnable, Path2Integrity develops new learning and campaign materials. To meet scientific standards, these materials must be evaluated. The group discussion is part of that evaluation and is intended to provide information about the sustainability and long-term efficiency of the learning units and campaign material. We thank you very much for supporting us in this process.

The group discussion will be audio recorded and held in *(insert English/German)*. On *(insert date of discussion)* you need approximately 1-2 hours for the discussion. Please read the attached informed consent form in advance and answer this short questionnaire (<https://path2integrity.eu/limesurvey/index.php/237937?lang=en>). In order to assign you to your group, please enter the following 2-digit group code in the appropriate place of the questionnaire: *(insert the respective 2-digit group code)*. Further preparations are not necessary.

Thank you very much for taking part in the group discussion and for supporting the Path2Integrity project!

For further communication with the persons interested in participating in the discussion, you should agree on a means of communication with the participants and exchange the necessary data. Follow the given regulations by your institution/P2I project when storing personal data.

6.2 Abstinance Principle

This principle means that you, as the group leader, should refrain from engaging in the discussion as much as possible. Do not take a position on statements or allow yourself to be included in the discussion. Appear interested and attentive, but easily withdraw from the center of attention. At best, try not to take notes, but follow the discussion attentively.

6.3 Question Types

Here we explain the different types of questions, when to ask them, and what the aim of each question is. Please use the questions only if the discussion is in a standstill. At best conditions you will not use any questions at all excluding the opening question.

6.3.1 Immanent Questioning

After introducing the initial research question (QUESTION) use immanent questions if the conversation comes to a standstill. Immanent questioning is a technique to reintroduce topics that have already been introduced by the participants. (What do you mean by X? Can you tell us more about it...) Avoid propositions in these questions. The questions should be kept "demonstratively vague", which means you should ask as unspecific as possible in order not to structure the answers or the main points of discussion.

Goal: Create a self-running discussion. Interventions should always serve to create a self-running and self-structured discussion by the group.

6.3.2 Exmanent Questioning

This type of question is only used when the group the self-guided discussion has ended, but questions that are relevant to the project's interest in knowledge have not been discursively dealt with by the group. The principle of demonstrative vagueness also applies to exmanent questions.

Goal: After the group's immanent potential has been exhausted, questions about the theoretical interest and/or topics can be asked for reasons of comparability. Here are some ideas for exmanent questions you can use:

- What (moral) expectations do you have of the scientific community?
- What impact do framework conditions have on your research?
- How important are guidelines in your academic life?
- What research principles are used in your discipline?
- How do you deal with it if you work with somebody who follows other principles/guidelines?
- Have you ever had any experience with scientific misconduct?
- How do you experience the discourse on conducting science?
- What goals do you pursue with scientific work?
- How important is research integrity for you and your work?
- How exactly do you follow the guidelines in your professional life as a researcher?
- Have you ever not followed the guidelines? Can you tell us about it?
- How well did you familiarise yourself with your guidelines?

6.3.3 Direct Questions (Phase)

This question type is used to clarify contradictions or inconsistencies in the discussion. The principle of demonstrative vagueness is discarded. Questions can be formulated precisely, pointedly and frontally and can be propositional. This phase is conducted after the "exmanent questions" phase.

Important: You don't have to use all of these types of questioning, but only those you consider relevant. In a best-case scenario, you will not need to use any of these questions.

6.4 Transcription

6.4.1 Clues

Planning

The transcription is likely to take time and persistence on your part. Plan your transcription times in advance. According to our experience, it is advisable to take regular breaks and spread the transcription over several days. Setting up a schedule and doing it regularly will make the transcription easier for you.

Speech Samples

To assign speech contributions, it is advisable to create speech samples for the participants before you start transcribing. Speech samples are short and characteristic audio files. Create an audio file for each person in the group discussion. You do not need to create separate recordings for this, you can take them from the group discussion recording. Speech samples facilitate transcription by allowing you to assign speech contributions to persons in difficult cases. Identification difficulties can occur due to the unfamiliarity of the persons, quiet or inaccurate speech contributions and simultaneousness of speech contributions. In these cases, speech samples can help to identify the person in question.

Transcription Programme

You can create a transcription with almost any writing programme. There are also special transcription programmes. A common programme, and a recommendation from us, is f4transkript. Which word processing programme you use is dependent on your preference and what is available to you.

Audio Playback Programme

Transcription programmes enable the audio file to be played back so the transcription can be written down. If you do not use a transcription programme, it is advisable to pay attention to two setting options when selecting the audio playback programme. Firstly, the programme should allow you to vary the volume, so that you can also hear very quiet contributions. Secondly, the programme should allow you to vary the playback speed. According to our experience, it is helpful to reduce the playback speed in order to have more time for writing and to be able to understand fast speech. Example: VLC Player

Transcription is essential for the application of the Documentary Method and the evaluation of the P2I project. It is a complex procedure. Please follow this guide and the transcription rules. It will be easier for you if you plan the transcription, select the programmes and their settings according to your preferences and possibilities.

Anonymisation

Ensure that all names and personal data are made anonymous during the transcription process. For the transcription each participant is assigned an anonymous code (First letter: Gender; Second letter: Alphabetical order (see Protocol)). The interviewer is anonymised with the letter Y. Use this code in the transcript to assign each statement to its corresponding author. If a person from the group is named during the discussion, use the above-mentioned anonymisation code for the named person. If a person is named who is not participating in the group discussion, the name is replaced by a pseudonym. Use a name from the same cultural context for the pseudonymisation (for example, Alexander can be pseudonymised as Henry, but not as Shakmi).

6.4.2 Transcription Rules

The following transcription rules are based on Przyborski & Wohlrab-Sahr¹ and Bohnsack²:

l	overlapping of speech acts
(.)	short break
(3)	seconds of a break
<u>no</u>	emphasised
no	loud in relation to the usual volume of the speaker
°no°	spoken very quietly
.	strongly dropping intonation
;	weakly dropping intonation
?	strongly rising intonation
,	weakly rising intonation
perha-	interruption of a word
oh=no	two or more words spoken as one
wou::ld	extension of a word, the frequency of “:” corresponds to the length of extension
(well)	uncertainty in transcription
()	word(s) not understood, according to length
((moans))	events beyond language
@no@	spoken while laughing
@(.)@	short laughter
@(3)@	laughter of 3 seconds

Example

The following transcription example is taken from Bohnsack³ (p. 112):

Text: Discoussiongroup “Sand” Side B3/6

Exerpt: “Marriage” (...)

- 1 Ym: Do you want to have family some day? (1)
 2 Bm: | yes, when (1) when our time has
 3 come for that, don´t know (.) I can´t tell (2)
 4 Am: | yes having a family is nice
 5 but it is not easy you know, (2)
 6 Ym: |mhm
 7 Bm: |I am unemployed anyway and so on
 8 (2) I think I won´t get married so soon.
 9 Am: |a family what does it mean a family°you know?°(1)
 10 °(no)°(3)

¹ Przyborski, A., & Wohlrab-Sahr, M. (2014). Qualitative Sozialforschung: Ein Arbeitsbuch (4., erw. Aufl.). München: Oldenbourg. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1524/9783486719550>

² Bohnsack, R., Pfaff, N., & Weller, W. (2010). Talk in Qualitative Research - TiQ. In R. Bohnsack, N. Pfaff, & W. Weller (Eds.), Qualitative Analysis and Documentary Method: In International Educational Research (p. 365). Opladen: Verlag Barbara Budrich.

³ Bohnsack, R. (2010). Documentary Method and Group Discussions. In R. Bohnsack, N. Pfaff, & W. Weller (Eds.), Qualitative Analysis and Documentary Method: In International Educational Research (pp. 99–124). Opladen: Verlag Barbara Budrich.

6.5 Protocol Template

Content

- Position of the participants anonymous (First letter: Gender; second letter: Alphabetical order)
- Position of the microphones and alignment
- Special speech characteristics of the individual persons
- The person who started the discussion: **MADE WITH 1**

Example

6.6 Informed Consent Form

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

This informed consent form is for persons of legal age participating in research conducted by the Path2Integrity project.

This Informed Consent Form has two parts:

- Information Sheet (to share information about the study with the participant)
- Data Protection Sheet

The participant can print out a copy of the full Informed Consent Form.

Study Title

Evaluation, WP6

Principal Investigator

Nicolaus Wilder, Institut für Pädagogik, Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel

Sponsor

EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation action
Grant agreement No. 824488

Project

Path2Integrity – Rotatory role-playing and role-models to enhance the research integrity culture

Participant Information Sheet

Introduction

I am Nicolaus Wilder, working for Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel. I am affiliated to a project called Path2Integrity. We conduct a study on learning and teaching research integrity in secondary schools and universities, which I invite you to take part in. I am collaborating in this study with colleagues at Hochschule Coburg (Germany), Syddansk Universitet (Denmark), 3C Compliance SL (Spain), Pensoft Publishers (Bulgaria), Fundacio Catalana per a la Recera i la Innovació (Spain), EUREC Office (Germany), Christian-Albrechts Universität zu Kiel (Germany) Instytut Badań Edukacyjnych (Poland), and Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin (Germany).

This form contains important information about the reasons for undertaking this study; what we will ask you to do if you decide to be in this study, and the way information about you will be used if you choose to participate. I am going to give you information and invite you to be part of this research. You do not have to decide today whether or not you will participate in the research. Before you decide, you can talk to anyone you feel comfortable with about the research.

This consent form may contain words that you do not understand. Please ask me to stop as we go through the information and I will take time to explain. If you have questions later, you can ask me or another researcher anytime.

Purpose of the Research

In a society marked by rapid technological change, for example with regard to big data and artificial intelligence, research and innovation are important. You might have heard of the term “knowledge society” in that regard. However, although it is widely recognized that research is very important, public confidence in science has been seriously undermined in recent years. One reason for this loss of confidence are numerous breaches of research integrity. You might have heard of some of these, asking yourself how they could go unnoticed for quite some time. We assume that at least part of the reason is that the research integrity culture in Europe is not as well-developed as it ideally should be. Thus, our study seeks to improve the research integrity culture in Europe by developing innovative learning materials that are based on role plays and role models. Furthermore, we are waging a campaign on research integrity in educational organizations.

Type of Research Intervention

This research will involve your participation in a group discussion that will take approximately 60 minutes. The research will be conducted at the Christian-Albrechts Universität zu Kiel or online.

Participant Selection

You are being invited to take part in this research because we feel that your experience as a researcher can contribute much to our understanding and knowledge of how research integrity can be learned effectively and how knowledge on research integrity can be spread.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary. It is your choice whether to participate or not. The choice that you make will have no bearing on your job, university or school career or on any work- or study-related evaluations or reports. You may change your mind later and stop participating even if you agreed earlier.

Procedures

We are asking you to help us learn more about learning and teaching research integrity. We are inviting you to take part in this research project. If you accept, you will be asked to fill in some background information online and do a group discussion.

Recording

We would like to video-record this focus group to make sure that we remember accurately all the information you provide. This is necessary for the method used to analyse the material. We will keep these tapes in locked cabinets and digital versions in password-protected areas on servers located in the European Union. They will only be used by researchers belonging to the Path2Integrity consortium. Once all personal data has been anonymised or erased, the data may be shared openly with other researchers. No videos, pictures or audio recordings enabling others to identify you will be shared. The video-recording is necessary for the data analysing. The participation is voluntary.

We may quote your remarks in presentations or articles resulting from this work. The data will be anonymised so that it will not be possible to identify you as the originator of a quote, unless you specifically request that you be identified by your true name.

Risks

To the best of our knowledge, the things you will be doing have no more risk of harm than you would experience in everyday life. However, you do not have to answer any question if you do not wish to do so, and that is also fine. You do not have to give us any reason for not responding to any question or for refusing to take part in the discussion.

As with all research, there is a chance that confidentiality of the information we collect from you could be breached – we will take steps to minimize this risk, as discussed in more detail below in this form.

Benefits

There will be no direct benefit to you, but your participation is likely to help us find out more about how to learn research integrity and improve the research integrity culture in Europe.

Reimbursements

No financial incentives are provided and no accruing expenses will be covered.

Confidentiality

Your personal data will be handled as confidentially as possible adhering to all pertinent international, European and national legislation. Whenever results of this study are published or presented, individual names and other personally identifiable information will not be used; i.e. the data will be anonymized.

To minimize the risks of breaching confidentiality, we will collect only personal data that we need for the purposes of the described research project. All partner institutions involved in the Path2Integrity project adhere to the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other pertinent international, European and national legislation. In particular, we ensure the following:

- Personal data are collected on a need to know basis only.
- Withdrawal rights and oblivion rights made compulsory by the European Court of Justice in 2014 are guaranteed.
- The merger of data sets containing personal data will be avoided in order to prevent any unforeseen personal information disclosure. Data may be made available for reuse by other researchers only if personal data has been anonymized or erased from the data set.

Hence, we will make sure that no answers you give can be traced back to you. All information you give will be assigned a unique code instead of your name. Only the researchers will know what your number is and we will store that information securely in password-protected digital archives on servers located in the European Union. Your personal data will not be shared with or given to anyone. Your data will be stored for an undefined period in accordance with prevalent laws.

We may share the data we collect from you for use in future research studies or with other researchers or journal editors. If we share the data that we collect about you, we will remove any personal information that could identify you before we share it.

Focus groups provide a particular challenge to confidentiality because once something is said in the group it becomes common knowledge. We like to encourage the group participants to respect confidentiality, but we cannot guarantee it.

We will ask you and others in the group not to talk to people outside the group about what was said in the group. We will, in other words, ask each of you to keep what was said in the group confidential. You should know, however, that we cannot stop or prevent participants who were in the group from sharing things that should be confidential.

Sharing the Results

We will share the results of our study with you upon your request once we have finished analysing the data. The project will run until December 2021 and results can be presented by February 2022. We will also share our research findings more broadly through publications and conferences. Data sets not containing any personal data may be shared via repository called Zenodo. However, all confidential information will remain confidential.

Right to Refuse or Withdraw

Participation in this study is voluntary. You do not have to answer any question you do not want to answer. If at any time and for any reason, you would prefer not to participate in this study, please feel free not to. If at any time you would like to stop participating, please tell the researcher. It is possible to take a break, stop and continue at a later date or stop altogether. You may withdraw from this study at any time. You will not be penalized in any way for deciding to stop participation. If you decide to withdraw from this study, the researchers will ask you if the information already collected from you can be used.

Who to Contact

If you have any questions, you can ask them now or later. If you wish to ask questions later, you may contact any of the following: Linda Zollitsch, at zollitsch@path2integrity.uni-kiel.de.

If you have any questions about your rights as a participant in this research, you can contact the following office: Nicolaus Wilder, at wilder@paedagogik.uni-kiel.de.

If you have any questions regarding data security that you do not wish to ask members of the research team, you may also contact Kiel university's Data Protection Officer at any time: Daniela Geißler at dgeissler@praesidium.uni-kiel.de.

Data Protection Sheet

What data do we collect?

This survey and the group discussion of Path2Integrity collects the following personal data:

- identification code, which is created by letters of your birthplace, your mothers name, the number of you older brothers, your eye-colour
- age, gender, country you identify with
- current profession, academic discipline / background

How do we collect your data?

You directly provide Path2Integrity with most of the data we collect. We collect data and process data when you:

- Voluntarily complete a survey or provide feedback
- Participate in the group discussion.

How will we use your data?

Path2Integrity collects your data so that we can:

- Compare your answers
- test the effectiveness of our learning materials
- gain a broader understanding of your concepts of good research practices
- share the data with other researchers for research purposes similar to Path2Integrity.

How do we store your data?

Path2Integrity securely stores your data at a server in the EU, which only authorised personnel can access.

Path2Integrity will keep your data for an undefined period in accordance with prevalent laws. We will delete your data once the Path2Integrity project and all project audits and reviews have been completed.

What are your data protection rights?

Path2Integrity would like to make sure you are fully aware of all of your data protection rights. Every participant is entitled to the following:

The right to access – You have the right to request Path2Integrity for copies of your personal data. We may charge you a small fee for this service.

The right to rectification – You have the right to request that Path2Integrity correct any information you believe is inaccurate. You also have the right to request Path2Integrity to complete the information you believe is incomplete.

The right to erasure – You have the right to request that Path2Integrity erase your personal data, under certain conditions.

The right to restrict processing – You have the right to request that Path2Integrity restrict the processing of your personal data, under certain conditions.

The right to object to processing – You have the right to object to Path2Integrity's processing of your personal data, under certain conditions.

The right to data portability – You have the right to request that Path2Integrity transfer the data that we have collected to another organization, or directly to you, under certain conditions.

If you make a request, we have one month to respond to you. If you would like to exercise any of these rights, please contact us at our email: zollitsch@path2integrity.uni-kiel.de

Or write to us: Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel
Path2Integrity, Linda Zollitsch
Olshausenstraße 75
24098 Kiel

How to contact us

If you have any questions about Path2Integrity's privacy policy, the data we hold on you, or you would like to exercise one of your data protection rights, please do not hesitate to contact us.

Email us at: wilder@paedagogik.uni-kiel.de.

Or write to us at: Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel
Nicolaus Wilder
Olshausenstraße 75
24098 Kiel

How to contact the appropriate authority

Should you wish to report a complaint or if you feel that Path2Integrity has not addressed your concern in a satisfactory manner, you may contact the data management officer.

Email us at: dgeissler@praesidium.uni-kiel.de.

Call us: +49 431 880-1773

Or write to us at: Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel
Syndika
24098 Kiel